

Scientific Intent

I. Expected Title of the Dissertation Thesis

Drought Effects on Carbon–Water Trade-Offs in European Forests: Observational Analysis and Process-Based Model Improvement for Water-Use Efficiency Projections

II. Topicality of the Researched Issue

Forests are central to the functioning of the climate system as they regulate the exchange of carbon, water, and energy between land and atmosphere. Their role in carbon sequestration is especially important in the context of climate change, yet this role depends strongly on the availability of water and on ecosystem resilience to climatic stress. Drought is therefore one of the most critical environmental pressures affecting forest ecosystems. In Europe, repeated extreme droughts during the last two decades have clearly shown that prolonged water limitation, elevated atmospheric demand, and heat extremes can substantially reduce ecosystem carbon uptake and alter forest functioning [1-3]. The 2003 European heatwave and drought caused a continent-scale reduction in gross primary productivity large enough to reverse several years of carbon sequestration [4], and the 2022 drought again demonstrated how temperature extremes and water deficits can strongly reduce carbon uptake in European forests [2]. These events underline that drought is not only a hydrological hazard but also a major control on the terrestrial carbon sink.

A particularly relevant concept in this context is water-use efficiency (WUE), because it captures the trade-off between carbon assimilation and water loss. Long-term eddy covariance studies have shown that ecosystem-scale WUE varies across sites and through time, and that forest WUE has increased in some temperate and boreal regions during recent decades, partly in response to rising atmospheric CO₂ [5-7]. However, these broad trends do not resolve the question of how drought events modify carbon–water coupling across different forest species, climates, and environmental settings. Existing studies suggest that drought can alter WUE in opposite directions depending on the timing, intensity, and duration of water limitation, and that these responses can be amplified by compound heat–drought conditions and by antecedent environmental states [8-9]. This means that the same drought metric does not necessarily imply the same ecosystem response. A stronger mechanistic understanding of historical WUE dynamics under drought is therefore essential if we want to predict future carbon sequestration more reliably.

At the same time, process-based ecosystem models remain imperfect in their representation of drought effects [10]. Although such models are indispensable for simulating forest carbon and water fluxes and for projecting ecosystem responses under climate change, they often struggle to reproduce the observed impacts of drought timing, severity, compound events, and legacy effects [11-13]. This limitation is not trivial: if models cannot adequately simulate the effects of historical droughts, their future projections of productivity, evapotranspiration (ET), and WUE are unlikely to be robust. Recent studies emphasize that soil moisture variability, plant hydraulic traits, and interactions between soil and atmospheric

dryness are central to carbon-cycle variability, while model uncertainty remains substantial because many drought-related processes are simplified or only partially represented [14]. For this reason, integrating long-term observations with targeted model evaluation and refinement is now a necessary step toward more realistic projections of forest carbon–water dynamics under climate change. The availability of standardized eddy covariance and meteorological observations from the ICOS ecosystem network makes this integration particularly feasible and scientifically valuable.

III. Research Hypothesis

This research is based on the central hypothesis that drought effects on carbon–water trade-offs in European forests are systematically controlled by drought timing, severity, antecedent environmental conditions, and compound climatic stressors, and that integrating observational evidence with ecosystem modelling can substantially improve the representation of drought processes and the reliability of future projections of WUE.

More specifically, the study hypothesizes that:

1. The response of WUE to drought varies systematically across forest ecosystems depending on the seasonal timing, duration, and severity of drought events.
2. Environmental conditions preceding drought events create legacy effects that influence ecosystem carbon–water dynamics.
3. Compound climatic events, particularly hot droughts, amplify drought impacts on ecosystem productivity and evapotranspiration.
4. Process-based ecosystem models underestimate drought impacts due to simplified representations of physiological and hydrological processes.
5. Constraining ecosystem models with site-based observational evidence can substantially improve simulations of drought effects on carbon–water cycling.

IV. Objectives of study

This thesis aims to identify the patterns and drivers of carbon–water cycling in European forests based on observations from ICOS eddy covariance infrastructure and to achieve substantial improvements in simulating carbon–water dynamics with an advanced process-based ecosystem model.

More specifically as below;

1. Identify patterns and drivers of historical drought impacts on WUE in European forest ecosystems.
2. Enhance simulation of drought effects on carbon–water cycles in the process-based ecosystem model Biome-BGCMuSo.
3. Attribute projected WUE trends for the twenty-first century to changing climatic conditions across European forest sites.

V. Planned methodological procedures

The thesis will be conducted through three interconnected work packages combining observational analysis, ecosystem modelling, and climate-change projections.

Work Package 1 – Observational analysis

Using multi-year eddy covariance observations from 14 ICOS forest sites, this work package will quantify historical drought impacts on water-use efficiency.

Key steps include:

1. Data acquisition and quality control of ICOS flux datasets.
2. Temporal homogenization and aggregation of flux observations.
3. Calculation of ecosystem WUE metrics.
4. Identification and characterization of drought events.
5. Analysis of legacy conditions and compound climatic events.
6. Statistical attribution of WUE variability to climatic drivers.

All analyses will be conducted in the R programming environment, ensuring a transparent and reproducible workflow. All preprocessed datasets (daily, monthly, and annual) will be archived in a public ZENODO repository to ensure transparency and reproducibility. This step is particularly valuable because ICOS flux data are distributed in raw form, often contain missing values, and are provided at different temporal resolutions; therefore, standardized and documented datasets will facilitate reuse by the wider scientific community.

Work Package 2 – Model evaluation and improvement

The process-based ecosystem model Biome-BGCMuSo will be implemented for the selected ICOS sites.

The methodology will include:

1. Model parameterization using site-specific vegetation, soil, and meteorological data.
2. Historical simulations of carbon and water fluxes.
3. Evaluation of model performance against ICOS observations.
4. Diagnosis of model weaknesses in representing drought responses.
5. Targeted parameter calibration and algorithm refinement.
6. Re-evaluation of improved simulations.

Work Package 3 – Future projections

The improved ecosystem model will be forced with future climate scenarios.

The analysis will include:

1. Simulation of future carbon and water fluxes.
2. Identification of projected drought impacts.
3. Analysis of future WUE trends.
4. Attribution of projected changes to climatic drivers.

Figure1. Conceptual workflow of the thesis framework

VI. Timeline of thesis

Figure 2. Timeline of research activities during the first year of the PhD project (September 2026–August 2027). The workflow includes the literature review (LR), data preparation (DP), data analysis (DA), preliminary ecosystem model implementation (Model), manuscript preparation (MP), manuscript writing, and manuscript submission (MS). The chart illustrates the sequential progression of tasks leading to the completion and submission of the first manuscript on historical water-use efficiency (WUE) based on ICOS observations.

Figure 3. Timeline of research activities during the second year of the PhD project (September 2027–August 2028). The work focuses on ecosystem model development and evaluation using the Biome-BGCMuSo model. Activities include model parameterization (Model.p), model calibration (Model.c), model evaluation (Model.e), and Data analysis (DA) parts. The results are then organized during the manuscript preparation phase (MP), which includes preparation of figures, tables, and results. This is followed by the manuscript writing phase (MW) and finally manuscript submission (MS), presenting model-based simulations of WUE during the historical period.

Figure 4: Timeline of research activities during the third year of the PhD project (September 2028–August 2029). The focus of this phase is on projecting ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE) under future climate scenarios. Activities include climate data preparation (DP), ecosystem model simulations under future scenarios (Model.s), and data analysis of projected WUE responses (DA). The results are organized during the manuscript preparation phase (MP), followed by manuscript writing (MR) and manuscript submission (MS), presenting the projected impacts of future climate conditions on ecosystem WUE.

Figure 5: Timeline of research activities during the fourth year of the PhD project (September 2029–August 2030). This final phase focuses on the integration and synthesis of research outcomes from historical analyses, model simulations, and future projections of ecosystem water-use efficiency (WUE). Activities include integrated data analysis (DA), manuscript preparation (MP), manuscript writing (MW), thesis writing (TW), and thesis revision (TR). The PhD project concludes with the doctoral thesis defense.

VII. Expected Results

The proposed research is expected to improve understanding of how drought influences carbon–water coupling in European forest ecosystems and to enhance the capability of ecosystem models to simulate drought impacts more realistically. By combining long-term eddy covariance observations with process-based ecosystem modeling, the project will provide new insights into the mechanisms controlling ecosystem WUE under both historical and future climate conditions. In addition, the research will contribute to improved modeling frameworks for assessing ecosystem responses to drought and climate change across European forests.

The PhD research is expected to result in four scientific publications in high-impact peer-reviewed journals, addressing observational analysis, model evaluation, future projections, and integrated synthesis of WUE dynamics:

- 1. Expected title of Paper for possible publication in Agricultural and Forest Meteorology (D1 Journal):**
Climatic drivers of drought-induced variability in forest water-use efficiency across European ecosystems
Alternative journal: *Global Change Biology*
- 2. Expected title of Paper for possible publication in Geoscientific Model Development (D1 journal):**
Improving ecosystem model representation of drought impacts on carbon–water fluxes in European forests
Alternative journal: *Ecological Modelling*
- 3. Expected title of Paper for possible publication in Forest Ecosystems (D1 journal):**
Projected changes in forest water-use efficiency under future climate scenarios in Europe
Alternative journal: *Environmental Research Letters*
- 4. Expected title of Paper for possible publication in Nature Communications Earth & Environment (Nature index):**
From historical observations to future projections: An integrated assessment of drought impacts on forest water-use efficiency across Europe
Alternative journal: *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*

Together, these publications will provide a comprehensive assessment of drought-driven changes in forest water-use efficiency, spanning observational evidence, model evaluation, future climate projections, and an integrated synthesis of ecosystem responses across European forest systems.

References

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